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Game engine design and application based on C++

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Abstract

With the rapid development of information technology, games have become an indispensable part of People's Daily life. The most important part of game software development is the design of game engine. This paper uses C++ high-level language to design and develop an efficient, stable and interactive game engine, using this game engine to develop a "hidden pairing" game software, game playability is high, this game engine has the characteristics of strong portability, robustness and scalability. All kinds of games can be designed and developed through game engine, which has a certain promotion effect on the development of game software industry

Keywords: Game Engine; C++; Hide Matchmaking Game Software; Hidden pairing

1. Introduction

With the development of science and technology, the development of the gaming industry has become increasingly important [1]. At present, most games on the market are developed using the Java language. However, in terms of controllability in games, the Java language is far inferior to C and C++ languages [2].

From the perspective of game design, the game engine is the heart of the game. If we compare a game to a car, the game engine is the engine of the car, directly determining its performance. The plot, levels, art, music, and gameplay that players experience in a game are all directly controlled and realized by the game engine. It plays the role of an engine, tying together all the elements in the game and directing them to work in an orderly manner. It ranges from controlling the volume level to calculating collisions, physical systems, and the relative positions of objects. The engine is the "main program used to control all game functions." Whether it is a 2D game or a 3D game, whether it is a role-playing game or an action shooter game, even the smallest game has such a piece of code that plays a controlling role[3-5].

2. Principles of Game Engine Design

All C++ programs under Windows start executing from the entry function WinMain(). The WinMain() function is mainly used for program initialization, displaying the main window, and entering the message loop to wait for and process messages. The operation mechanism of Windows applications is shown in Figure 1.

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Figure 1 Running mechanism of windows applications

In the development of Windows applications, it is necessary to create program windows, and game programs are no exception. To establish a window, it is necessary to use window structures and related Windows API functions for creating windows, which provide an interface layer for communication between user applications and the operating system. When the program needs the operating system to perform a certain function, it is generally accomplished through API calls.

To create a window, one must first establish a window structure that contains all the relevant information about the window, such as menu styles. After the window structure is defined, the registration functions `RegisterClass()` or `RegisterClassEx()` are used to register it in the system. Once these preparatory steps are completed, the `CreateWindow()` function can be called to create the window. The window will not be displayed immediately after creation; it is also necessary to call the `ShowWindow()` function and the `UpdateWindow()` function to display the program window and update the client area of the window, respectively.

After the window is established, the program enters the message loop, waiting in the loop to receive and process messages. The typical message loop of a Windows application mainly involves three functions: `GetMessage()`, `TranslateMessage()`, and `DispatchMessage()`. The `GetMessage()` function retrieves messages from the thread's message queue, the `TranslateMessage()` function interprets the messages, converting virtual-key messages into character messages, and finally, the `DispatchMessage()` function sends the messages to the corresponding window procedure for further processing. In this process, the `PeekMessage()` function may also be used. The `PeekMessage()` function is similar to the `GetMessage()` function; it checks the thread message queue and, if a message exists, places it in the specified structure. In the program, message sending functions such as `PostMessage()` or `SendMessage()` can also be used to send specific messages.

After a message occurs in the program, the `GetMessage()` or `PeekMessage()` function will pass the message to the window, and the message handling function in the window structure will immediately process it.

An excellent game cannot be separated from a high-performance game engine. The game engine is the "main program used to control all game functions." That is, the game engine breaks down a game into multiple events, including engine initialization, parameter initialization, interaction, logic, rendering, resource release, and game over. The following figure shows the game engine architecture designed in this paper, as shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2 Game engine architecture

When the game starts running, the initialization event is responsible for loading the game's graphics and sounds, creating the game engine, that is, initializing the game engine, and creating the game window. The construction of the game engine mainly involves initializing engine parameters and constructing instances of the engine class, followed by the creation of the game window. After the window is successfully created, it becomes convenient to initialize the game parameters in the desired way. When the game is minimized or sent to the background and then restored, game pause and activation events will occur. When the game needs to draw itself, a game screen drawing event will occur. During the game, the player's control of the game mainly relies on the mouse and keyboard, which triggers game interaction events. Finally, before the game ends, the resources allocated in the program will be released.

During the operation of the game, the initialization process of the game can be divided into two parts: the construction of the game engine and the creation of the game window, both of which are encapsulated in the game engine and can be called by game developers in specific designs.

When program developers design game programs, game parameter initialization, game logic implementation, and game screen drawing, as functions unique to games, need to have these function methods clearly defined, providing a unified interface for program design. Functions such as the entry function `WinMain()` and the message processing function `WindowProc()`, which cannot be implemented in the game engine class, must be external functions. Due to the particularity of game programs, their `WinMain()` function is different from that of ordinary programs, which will be detailed in the following text [6-8].

Message processing in games is similar to that in general applications, all handled in the message processing function `WndProc()`. In game programs, the most basic message functions are game parameter initialization, screen drawing, game interaction, game pause, and game end with resource release. Game parameter initialization occurs after the game engine is constructed and the window is created. Since games vary, the specific functions need to be perfected by game developers according to design requirements [6]. Screen rendering is crucial for game programs, directly affecting players' gaming experience and interest. There are generally two ways of screen rendering: one is drawing in the game loop, and the other is drawing in response to the window drawing message `WM_PAINT`. During the operation of the game, the entire process is the interaction between the player and the game, which mainly relies on the mouse and keyboard, so the processing of mouse and keyboard messages is equally important. Sometimes when players need to leave the game window, the game execution needs to be paused and the game window suspended. Like general Windows programs, releasing the resources allocated in the program before the game ends is indispensable.

3. Game Engine Construction and Implementation

After designing the game engine in this paper, the Engine game engine is implemented through programming in the C++ advanced programming language.

3.1. Game Engine Construction and Parameterization

- The construction of the game engine mainly involves initializing engine parameters and building engine instances.

Engine (HINSTANCE hInstance, LPTSTR szWindowClass, LPTSTR szTitle, WORD wIcon, WORD wSmallIcon, BOOL bFullScreen, int nColorbit, int nWidth, int nHeight) {...}

- Creating the game window is mainly accomplished by the window creation function CreateWnd():
 - CreateGameWindow(){
 - wcAPP.cbSize = sizeof(wcAPP); // Assign values to window properties
 - wcAPP.lpszClassName = m_szWindowClass; // Set the window class name
 - wcAPP.style = CS_HREDRAW; // Define the window style
 - wcAPP.lpfnWndProc = WndProc; // Specify the message processing function
 - wcAPP.hInstance = m_hInstance;
 - wcAPP.cbWndExtra = 0;
 - wcAPP.cbClsExtra = 0;
 - /* Use the DEVMODE structure to set the screen display mode */
 - DEVMODE DevMode; // Clear the memory of the DevMode structure
 - ZeroMemory(&DevMode, sizeof(DevMode)); // Set the DevMode storage space to store screen property data
 - DevMode.dmSize = sizeof(DevMode); // Use the current screen display mode to fill the DevMode
 - EnumDisplaySettings(NULL, ENUM_CURRENT_SETTINGS, &DevMode);
 - BOOL bDisplayChange = FALSE; // Flag to indicate whether the screen display mode has changed
 - // Call the function CreateWindow to establish the window
 - hWnd = CreateWindow(m_szWindowClass, m_szTitle, dwWinStyle, nPosX, nPosY, nWndWidth, nWndHeight, NULL, NULL, m_hInstance, NULL);
 - ShowWindow(hWnd, SW_SHOWNORMAL);
 - UpdateWindow(hWnd);

Creating the game window requires setting the game display mode. If the game is in full-screen display mode, it is also necessary to set the display screen properties, set the screen size to the window size, and set the corresponding color mode. If it is not full-screen display, the window should be set to display in the center of the screen.

- Finally, use a GmInitialize() function to define content during the game, which facilitates subsequent development.

3.2. Game Engine Operation Mechanism

In the operation mechanism of the game engine, the main difference between its WinMain() function and that in ordinary programs lies in the processing of the message loop.

```
WinMain(HINSTANCE hInstance, HINSTANCE hPrevInstance, LPSTR lpCmdline, int nCmdShow) {
```

```
MSG msg;
```

```
/* Initialize the game */
```

```
if (!GmInitialize(hInstance)) return false;
```

```
/* Message loop */
```

```
if (PeekMessage(&msg, NULL, 0, 0, PM_REMOVE)) {
```

```

if (msg.message == WM_QUIT) // If it is a quit message, exit

    break;

TranslateMessage(&msg);

DispatchMessage(&msg);

}

}

```

First, the `GmInitialize()` function is called to create the game engine and initialize the game framework. Then, the game enters the message loop. By using `PeekMessage()` to receive messages, the game loop continues to execute when no messages occur, rather than waiting for messages. When messages occur, the game loop switches to process the messages; when no messages occur, the message loop is executed.

3.3. Game Engine Message Interaction

In the message interaction of the game engine, the message processing function `WndProc()` is used. The following introduces some commonly used messages in game programs:

```

WndProc(HWND hWnd, UINT message, WPARAM wParam, LPARAM lParam) {

    /* Use a switch statement to judge messages and perform corresponding processing */

    switch (message) {

        case WM_CREATE: // Window creation message

            Engine::GetEngine()->SetWindow(hWnd);

            GmStart(hWnd);

            break;

        case WM_PAINT: // Window drawing message

            HDC hDC;

            PAINTSTRUCT ps;

            hDC = BeginPaint(hWnd, &ps);

            GmPaint(hDC);

            EndPaint(hWnd, &ps);

            break;

        case WM_LBUTTONDOWN: // Left mouse button down message

            MouseLButtonDown(hWnd, LOWORD(lParam), HIWORD(lParam), wParam);

            break;

        case WM_SETFOCUS:

            GmActive(hWnd);

```

```

Engine::GetEngine()->SetPause(FALSE);

break;

case WM_KEYDOWN: // Keyboard key press message

    if (wParam == VK_ESCAPE) // Check if the Esc key is pressed

        SendMessage(hWnd, WM_CLOSE, NULL, NULL);

    break;

case WM_KILLFOCUS:

    GmPause(hWnd);

    Engine::GetEngine()->SetPause(TRUE);

    break;

case WM_CLOSE:

    if (GameWindowClose(hWnd))

        DestroyWindow(hWnd);

    break;

case WM_DESTROY:

    GmEnd();

    PostQuitMessage(0);

    break;

default:

    return DefWindowProc(hWnd, message, wParam, lParam);

}

}

```

4. Application of the Game Engine --- "Hidden Pair" Game Software

The game engine designed and developed in this paper is used to implement a "Hidden Pair" game software.

4.1. Design Scheme of the Hidden Pair Game Software

The Hidden Pair game is a casual puzzle game with elements of the traditional "spot-the-difference" series. It is simple to operate and easy to get started. The game initially combines elements of classic picture-finding series games and RPG game elements. Players cultivate characters, complete tasks, and upgrade various skills in the game. They can also use props to help overcome difficulties and find targets when facing challenges.

The Hidden Pair game is developed using the C++ advanced programming language, employing methods such as game engines, arrays, functions, and structures to create an intellectual game. The following figure shows the running window of the Hidden Pair game software, as shown in Figure 3.

4.3. Algorithm Implementation of the Game Software

```

/* Initialize patterns and positions */
// Initialize random number seed
srand((unsigned)time(NULL));
for(i=0; i<ROWS*COLS; i++){
    do{
        // Randomly generate a position number m among the 18 positions
        m = rand() % (ROWS*COLS);
    } while(array2[m] == 0); // Array array2 is used to mark whether the position is occupied
    // Mark the image sequence number corresponding to this position
    array1[m] = i;
    // Mark this position as occupied
    array2[m] = 0;
}
for(i=0; i<ROWS; i++){
    for(j=0; j<COLS; j++){
        // Array g_nCardPattern is used to represent the positions of the 18 images
        // Pass the value at this position in array array1 to array g_nCardPattern
        g_nCardPattern[i][j] = array1[i*6+j];
    }
}
// Candidate patterns
int arr[18];
for(i=0; i<3; i++){
    do {
        // Randomly generate a position number n
        n = rand() % 18;
    } while(arr[n] == 0); // Check if the position is occupied
    // Mark the image sequence number corresponding to this position
    g_nCardarray[i] = n;
}

```

```
// Mark this position as occupied  
arr[n] = 0;  
}  
The checkposition() function: // Check the position of the image corresponding to the candidate pattern  
int checkposition(int num){  
    int i, j;  
    for(i=0; i<ROWS; i++){  
        for(j=0; j<COLS; j++){  
            /*Match the image sequence number at each position with the target image sequence number according to the  
            position order*/  
            if(g_nCardPattern[i][j] == num){  
                return(i*6+j);  
                break;  
            }  
        }  
    }  
    return 0;  
}
```

The game is debugged and runs in the Windows system environment. The game interface is aesthetically pleasing, the operation is convenient, and the stability and robustness of the game are good. The game design adds new features such as coins and time, enhancing the challenge of the game, making it more playable and enjoyable for players

5. Conclusion

This paper designs and develops an Engine game engine based on C++. The designed game engine can be used to develop various types of games. Through the design and implementation of the Hidden Pair game software, it can be concluded that the game engine operates stably, with strong portability, good robustness, and high expandability. The code reuse rate of the game engine has been significantly improved, making the development and maintenance of games more convenient. This provides a certain reference for the development and design of other games.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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